

Can Near Surface Air Temperature act as Proxy to Anthropogenic influence in the mangrove dominated Indian Sundarbans?

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Abstract

The analyses the secondary data collected from the archives of University of Calcutta and Techno India University, West Bengal and several relevant literatures over a period of more than three decades (1984-2016). We consider Sagar Island as the representative of Indian Sundarbans region for this study. We observe an increasing trend in near surface air temperature in all the three seasons, which may be attributed to change of land use pattern due to intense industrialization, unplanned urbanization and expansion of tourism units coupled with establishment of shrimp farms in all the regions at the cost of mangroves. The adverse impacts of such anthropogenic activities related rise in near surface air temperature on marine estuarine biotic community is discussed in a qualitative manner.

Keywords: Mangroves, Near Surface Air Temperature, Sagar Island, Temporal Variation.

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1. Introduction

Air temperature is basically a measurement to detect the hotness or coldness of the air. It describes the kinetic energy of the gas molecules that constitute the air. Air temperature regulates several weather parameters like the rate of evaporation, relative humidity, wind speed/direction and precipitation. It is a function of the amount and strength of the sunlight heating the earth and atmospheric conditions such as cloud cover and humidity that trap the heat energy. It has also been documented that greenhouse gases trap heat near the Earth surface. People are adding several types of greenhouse gases to the atmosphere, and each gas's effect on climate change depends on three main factors namely the amount/quantum of gas added, the duration of gas addition and the potential of the added gas in terms of warming. [1] Carbon dioxide is one of the major greenhouse gases that are emitted by vehicles, industries, power plants etc., which traps heat in the air. [2]

The planet Earth is getting warmer due to climate change caused by anthropogenic activities or natural variability. However, the rate has steadily increased since the beginning of the industrial revolution. A study conducted by the researchers of NASA's Goddard Institute of Space Studies (GISS), reveals that the average global temperature on earth has increased by about 0.8°C. Two-thirds of the warming has occurred since 1975 at a rate roughly between 0.15% to 0.20% per decade. Generally warming is greater over land than over the ocean because water is slower to absorb and release heat (Thermal inertia). [3]

The Indian Sundarbans at the apex of Bay of Bengal is a deltaic complex dominated by mangrove vegetation. Temporal variation of air temperature in Sundarbans has been recorded from 11.96 to 37.0 °C. [4] This deltaic complex experiences maximum air temperature value during premonsoon followed by monsoon and postmonsoon. [2, 5-7] The present paper is a first-order analysis of the temporal variation of near surface air temperature in Sagar Island over a period of more than three decades (1984-2016).

2. Materials and methods

2.1 Data sources and quality

In this paper, a data set of more than three decades on near surface air temperature in Indian Sundarbans region has been considered for a first order analysis. This time frame is in accordance with the minimum standard norms of climate related researches. The World Metrological Organization (WMO) and the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) define "climate" as the average state of the weather over time with the period generally being 30 years, (although for some marine climate parameters such as storminess, longer averages are required [8]. More than three decades of data (1984 - 2016) were compiled from the archives of the Department of Marine Science, University of Calcutta and Techno India University, West Bengal for this study. A number of studies on different aspects of the Sundarban complex have been published over the years, which include description of the data (and methods) at different times over the past three decades. [4, 9-19]

3. Results

The present pattern of near surface air temperature clearly reflects an increasing trend through seasons in the study site, Fig. (1).

In premonsoon, the increment is 0.09 °C/yr, while in both monsoon and postmonsoon seasons the increments are 0.07 °C/yr.

The near surface air temperature exhibited an increasing trend with the passage of time. This may be attributed to change of land use pattern, deforestation (preferably mangrove deforestation for the sake of shrimp culture) unplanned urbanization, intense industrialization and expansion of tourism units. In addition, the rise of temperature is also attributed to gradually increase of atmospheric carbon dioxide in this deltaic complex. [20]

Figure 1. Temporal variation of near surface air temperature in Sagar Island. [20]

4. Discussion

Sagar Island is the largest island of Indian Sundarbans with an area of 224.3 sq.km. (marked with 'S' in Fig. (2)). The island was dominated by mangroves and about 25 species of mangroves were documented in the southernmost tip of Sagar Island near the light house area. [2] However, due to expansion of shrimp farms in an unplanned manner, particularly in the Chemaguri region (88° 09' 46.64"E; 21° 38' 54.86"N), there has been a massive deforestation of mangroves. The intense rates of urbanization, mushrooming of tourism activities and construction of a proposed harbor have reduced the mangrove patches in Sagar Island to a great extent, Fig. (2).

The change of land use pattern at the cost of blue carbon may be one of the reasons behind the gradual rise of near surface air temperature. The increase of air temperature as revealed from the data sets of more than three decades are 9.23%, 7.12% and 8.07% in premonsoon, monsoon and postmonsoon seasons respectively. Another important feature in the graph of premonsoon air temperature is an abrupt spike in 2009, which may be attributed to super cyclone Aila that passed across lower Gangetic delta during 25th and 26th May, 2009. [21]

Global atmospheric temperatures and CO₂ concentrations have risen throughout the last 50

years [22, 23], which has triggered the rise of air temperature. Simultaneously, the World's oceans have experienced a net warming [24-26]. Regional increases in temperature have been documented in the southwest Pacific Ocean and north Atlantic Ocean [27, 28]. For the last 20-30 years, the western Mediterranean Sea temperatures have been rising [29], which is reflected in the presence and abundance of ectothermic marine life [30]. For example, off the coast of France, two thermophilic algal species, several thermophilic echinoderm species, and some thermophilic fishes have increased in abundance, while other thermophilic species are being observed for the first time. [30]

Estimates of future surface air temperature increases range from 1 to 7 °C, depending on the hypothesized atmospheric carbon dioxide contents. [31-34] Air temperatures are expected to increase ocean warming, most significantly in the upper 500-800 m [35]. However, even slight warming of deeper oceanic layers will have a huge impact on the earth's energy budget due to the mass of water they contain [24, 35, 36]. Ocean circulations are predicted to shift, possibly interacting with land masses, creating a north-south thermal asymmetry [35]. For example, the northern boundary of the Gulf Stream has shifted slightly northward in recent decades [37].

Figure 2. Temporal changes in vegetation (Blue Carbon) of Sagar Island. [57]

Climate change will affect individuals, populations and communities through the individual’s physiological and behavioral responses to environmental changes. [38] Extremes in environmental factors, such as elevated water temperature, low dissolved oxygen or salinity and pH, can have deleterious effects on fishes [39]. Sub-optimal environmental

conditions can decrease foraging, growth, and fecundity, alter metamorphosis, and affect endocrine homeostasis and migratory behavior [40-42]. These organismal changes directly influence population and community structure by their associated effects on performance, patterns of resource use, and survival [43, 44].

Estuarine and coastal regions are extremely productive because they receive inputs from several primary production sources and detrital food webs. Yet, these systems present the biota with a harsh environment, forcing organisms to evolve physiological or behavioral adaptations to cope with wide ranging physical and chemical variables [45]. Due to water circulation and oceanic volume changes, estuarine and coastal systems are predicted to experience a loss of marsh and intertidal habitat, a greater marine intrusion or freshwater plumes, and increased eutrophication, hypoxia, and anoxia [46-49]. The close relationship between laboratory-based measurements of fish's responses to temperature and the same species thermal distributional limits in their native habitats has been demonstrated [50]. Because many native organisms currently live near their tolerance limits, estuarine and coastal ecosystems will likely exhibit responses earlier to regional changes, including native species loss and exotic species increases [47, 51].

Marine pelagic systems are susceptible to climate change through extreme events and the contraction or expansion of oceanic zones. For example, sea temperature changes driven by variations in the North Atlantic Oscillation (NAO)

have been linked to fluctuations in cod (*Gadus morhua*) recruitment and habitat shifts off Labrador and Newfoundland [52]. On the west coast of Canada and Alaska, the Gulf of Alaska is exhibiting increased temperature and decreased salinity levels. The result is seen in shallower mixed layers, which lead to a reduced nutrient supply [53], impacting primary production levels and altering food webs [54-56].

The rising trend of near surface air temperature in the mangrove dominated Indian Sundarbans region (as revealed from the data bank generated from Sagar Island) has the possibility of altering the biotic community in this designated World Heritage Site of Indian sub-continent. Hence a proper management action plan is of great important to minimize and control the emission from brick kilns, industries, fishing vessels and trawlers, which are the main point sources of GHG in this deltaic complex, Fig. (3). Also there is a need to develop nursery of blue carbon on large scale basis, which can act as GHG and temperature regulators.

Figure 3. Point sources of GHGs in and around Indian Sundarbans. [58]

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